

THERMOELECTRIC BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR AIRCRAFT APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY

The thermoelectric behaviour of CFRP samples is investigated experimentally with the support of coupled numerical simulations. The temperatures fields resulting from applied electrical DC currents are measured by infrared thermography: temperatures in the range of 190-200°C are measured for currents up to 8A, with a total resistance of around 0.5 Ω .

Keywords: thermoelectricity, DC currents, composite electrical resistance, multiphysical modelling, infrared thermography

INTRODUCTION

Electrical currents are widely employed for health monitoring of composite materials and structures [1, 2]. In this case, small currents (mA) are applied for a very short lapse of time and the voltage measured; however, not much is known about the direct effects of relatively high currents (A) on the behaviour of composite materials for structural applications. The present paper describes the thermal effects produced by currents up to 8A on CFRP samples for aircraft applications. The temperature fields are measured by infrared thermography, experiments are supported by coupled numerical simulations.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

16 plies [(0/90)₄]_s CFRP samples (T300/914) (average dimensions: 180mm*15mm*1.8mm with standard glass/epoxy tabs) are subjected to constant currents from 1A up to 8A and, for each value of current, the induced transient temperature fields are measured by infrared thermography. At both ends, samples are equipped with metallic (copper based) electrode contacts produced by electrodepositing (around 50 μ m thick) through which currents are injected. The resistance of the sample, evaluated by the rule of mixtures excluding contact and wire resistance, is around 0.3-0.4 Ω , depending on the sample dimensions.

DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the temperature evolution as a function of time profile at several points along a composite sample for all the tested currents. The temperature distribution is uniform along the sample, except at the glass/epoxy tabs, where temperatures are systematically lower (up to 20°C difference). At 8A the maximum temperature, measured at the centre of the sample, is around 190°C. The total measured resistance (including the sample, the electrode contacts and the wires) is around 0.5 Ω for all the tested currents all along the measured temperature range; in particular, the contact resistance is low and does not promote localised heating at the samples ends. Coupled thermoelectric numerical simulations in ABAQUS and calculations based on simple analytical models reproduce well the temperature fields observed experimentally and the heterogeneity introduced by the glass/epoxy tabs: such tabs are characterised by very low coefficients of thermal and electrical conduction and, most of all, do not contribute to the Joule heating.

Figure 1: Temperature evolution as a function of time for all the tested currents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present research is carried out within the FRAE VICOMTHE Research Program in collaboration with AIRBUS, LIM-ENSAM Paris, LGMT Toulouse. All partners of the research are gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. Schulte, K., Baron, C. (1989) Composites Science and Technology, 36: 63-76
2. Xia, Z., Curtin, W.A. (2007) Composites Science and Technology, 67: 1518-1529